

Interview guideline – Harnessing tacit knowledge in sustainable product engineering

General section 1 – narrative method

- How have you personally experienced topic of sustainability in product engineering in your work?
- How did you first meet requirements or issues relating to sustainable product engineering?
- When you think back over the last few years, what technologies or changes had a particular impact on sustainable product engineering?
- Can you give examples that show how sustainability aspects have been successfully integrated into a project?
- When you look back on recent years, what comes to mind when you think about sustainable product engineering? What stands out to you as significant, whether in a positive or negative sense?
- How do you acquire the knowledge that is important for sustainable product engineering?
- Go back to the beginning of your career: Which experiences were particularly significant for sustainability, whether positive or negative?
- Have there been any changes in the engineering process in recent years regarding sustainability?

General Part 2 – Critical Incident Technique

- Think of a situation in which you or your team were particularly successful in implementing sustainability criteria in product engineering. Please describe the process as precise as possible: What was the trigger, how did you proceed, and what was the result?
- Have there been situations in which the implementation of sustainability aspects was particularly difficult or perhaps even failed? What factors contributed to this?
- Think of a project in which a decision regarding sustainability was hotly debated or controversial. How was this situation resolved?
- When you look back on these formative experiences, what learning processes or changes resulted from them for your future work?

Presentation of the product example

Material

No knowledge	Little knowledge	Basic knowledge	Extensive knowledge	Expert knowledge

- Which materials would you choose for the engineering of the **product example** to make it as sustainable as possible?
- Which properties of the materials are particularly important? What do you need to pay attention to?

- What differences are there in auxiliary materials if you want to pay particular attention to sustainability?

Energy

No knowledge	Little knowledge	Basic knowledge	Extensive knowledge	Expert knowledge

- Are there noticeable differences in performance when engineering is more sustainable? If so, what are they and how can they be remedied?
- How can energy consumption be minimized in the production of **product example**? What requirements must be met or observed to achieve this?
- How can losses be minimized?
- How is a sustainable energy balance achieved?
- What needs to be in place so that the energy leaving the system, such as waste heat, can be used?

Signal

No knowledge	Little knowledge	Basic knowledge	Extensive knowledge	Expert knowledge

- What sustainability aspects do you consider when selecting and processing signals in mechatronic systems?
- To what extent does signal processing (e.g., measurement, control, or regulation technology) influence the energy and resource consumption of your product?
- What criteria do you use to select sustainable sensor and signal transmission technologies?
- How can data exchange between **product examples** be made as sustainable as possible?

Interfaces

No knowledge	Little knowledge	Basic knowledge	Extensive knowledge	Expert knowledge

- How would you design the interfaces of the **product example** to be as sustainable as possible, both within the system and in relation to the environment?
- What sustainable criteria do you consider when defining and designing interfaces?
- What conflicts of interest arise between functionality, compatibility, and resource conservation when making interface decisions?
- What role does the modularity of interfaces play in the engineering of durable and repairable products?
- Do you use standardized interfaces to promote component interchangeability and reusability? What requirements do these have?

- How do you take into account the updateability and expandability of interfaces in order to extend the service life of the overall system?

Stakeholders

No knowledge	Little knowledge	Basic knowledge	Extensive knowledge	Expert knowledge

- Do customers influence the path to sustainability? Does this result in more requirements?
- Are stakeholders already concerned with sustainable product engineering? How does this influence your work?

Planning

No knowledge	Little knowledge	Basic knowledge	Extensive knowledge	Expert knowledge

- How do you ensure that sustainable materials are available when developing the **product example**? How does sustainability influence this?
- Are there special requirements for the planning framework in sustainable product engineering?
- How does sustainability influence target costs? What needs to be considered?

Life cycle assessment

No knowledge	Little knowledge	Basic knowledge	Extensive knowledge	Expert knowledge

- How would you conduct a life cycle assessment for **product example**?

Purchasing

No knowledge	Little knowledge	Basic knowledge	Extensive knowledge	Expert knowledge

- To what extent is attention already being paid to sustainable materials or similar factors in purchasing?
- How are make-or-buy decisions or decisions about local suppliers made in terms of sustainability?

Manufacturing

No knowledge	Little knowledge	Basic knowledge	Extensive knowledge	Expert knowledge

- How would you define manufacturing processes for **product example** to ensure a high level of sustainability?
- How do you ensure that product design is suitable for manufacturing with regard to sustainability?
- How are manufacturing processes selected in sustainable product engineering?
- What quality and tolerance requirements are set to ensure that products are sustainable?

Assembly

No knowledge	Little knowledge	Basic knowledge	Extensive knowledge	Expert knowledge

- How can the assembly of **product example** be made as simple and sustainable as possible? How is simple/sustainable disassembly ensured?
- How can these characteristics be implemented in the installation?

Transport

No knowledge	Little knowledge	Basic knowledge	Extensive knowledge	Expert knowledge

- How would you organize the transport of the **product example** to take sustainability into account? What conditions must be in place or taken into consideration?
- To what extent are transport routes and means of transport included for greater sustainability?
- How would you design packaging for **product example** to be resource-efficient?

Control

No knowledge	Little knowledge	Basic knowledge	Extensive knowledge	Expert knowledge

- What roles do measurement and testing options play in your engineering process when it comes to ensuring sustainable product characteristics?
- How do you define sustainability criteria (e.g., energy efficiency, material consumption, service life) in your testing and control concepts?
- What testing methods do you use to assess environmental impacts (e.g., energy consumption, emissions, wear and tear) during use?

Software deployment

No knowledge	Little knowledge	Basic knowledge	Extensive knowledge	Expert knowledge

- To what extent do your software provision strategies (e.g., installation, updates, distribution) influence sustainability?
- What role does the choice of platforms, tools, and standards play in sustainable software delivery?

Maintenance

No knowledge	Little knowledge	Basic knowledge	Extensive knowledge	Expert knowledge

- What needs to be in place to enable sustainable maintenance of the **product example**?
- What is being done to ensure the availability of components throughout the entire product life cycle?
- How would you integrate aspects of predictive maintenance into the engineering of the **product example**?

Environment of use

No knowledge	Little knowledge	Basic knowledge	Extensive knowledge	Expert knowledge

- How can the operating conditions for the **product example** be designed to be sustainable?
- How can sustainable commissioning be planned for the **product example**?

Recycling

No knowledge	Little knowledge	Basic knowledge	Extensive knowledge	Expert knowledge

- What do you need to consider in the engineering of the **product example** to ensure its recyclability? How would you implement this in concrete terms?
- How would you implement almost complete disassembly for **product example**?
- What experience do you have with the recycling compatibility of composite materials and their recyclability?

Geometry

No knowledge	Little knowledge	Basic knowledge	Extensive knowledge	Expert knowledge

- How would you develop the dimensions, installation space, and layout of the **product example** to place particular emphasis on sustainability?
- How can the installation space be used in a particularly sustainable way?
- How would you miniaturize (reduce the size of the structures while maintaining their function) the **product example** to save resources?

Mechanics (forces, shape, kinematics, kinetics)

No knowledge	Little knowledge	Basic knowledge	Extensive knowledge	Expert knowledge

- How would you take aspects of lightweight construction into account when developing the **product example**?
- How would you save resources?
- How do loads, friction, speed, and vibrations influence sustainable product engineering?

Electrics/electronics

No knowledge	Little knowledge	Basic knowledge	Extensive knowledge	Expert knowledge

- What sustainability criteria would you consider when selecting and designing electrical and electronic components for **product example**? How would you implement them?
- How would you implement the most sustainable possible circuitry for **product example**?

Software

No knowledge	Little knowledge	Basic knowledge	Extensive knowledge	Expert knowledge

- Under what conditions is sustainable hardware selected?
- What role does sustainability play in the engineering and design of your software solutions?
- What measures do you take to ensure that software remains usable in the long term (e.g., compatibility with older versions, continuous updates)?

Security

No knowledge	Little knowledge	Basic knowledge	Extensive knowledge	Expert knowledge

- How can you ensure environmental safety with **product example**?